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CREATIVITY IN ART EDUCATION – IDEALS AND REALITY

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Abstract

One of the challenges of contemporary education is the development of creative thinking. Creativity is often discussed, but sometimes it is misunderstood. Future teachers often have insufficient or incorrect information about it to be able to assess and develop it properly. The article first defines creativity and the possibilities for its development, and points to the reality of school practice. In its research part, the article examines the views of university students – future art education teachers – on selected aspects of creativity: originality, the assessment of creativity, and the development of creativity. The research findings lead to recommendations for practice – to focus on familiarizing students not only with ways to develop creativity but also with how to assess it.

Keywords: creativity, attitude, future teachers, art education.

Introduction

At the Department of Creative Arts and Art Education, Faculty of Education, Constantine the Philosopher University in Nitra, we prepare future teachers of visual arts for primary schools, secondary schools, and for the visual arts departments of elementary art schools. An important part of our education also involves focusing on students' personal development. Currently, there is an emphasis on critical thinking and creativity in the education of young people. The development of creativity is emphasized across all types of disciplines that are part of the study programs "Teaching of Visual Arts (Combined Study)" and "Art Education".

Creativity relates to every aspect of life, as it is applied across a broad spectrum of areas including science, art, mass media, fashion, products, etc., and everyone experiences creativity differently. In practical life, we face numerous situations that require quick and resourceful solutions. Individuals who possess not only specialization but also key competencies such as creativity, communication skills, critical thinking, and others, are valuable to the job market (Hrehová, 2016). Meanwhile, employers automatically expect all university graduates to possess these competencies. As recently as the late 20th century, creativity was perceived primarily as the domain of art and artistic subjects; however, today it is required in all disciplines, from both students and teachers, throughout the process of teaching, learning, and applying knowledge (Štěpánková, 2022). The development of society depends significantly on the preparedness of young people; therefore, the development of creativity within the

population is also linked to the higher education community. Future teachers will convey information to our children, while also shaping their personalities during formal education. The more teachers understand creative learning and motivation, the better they can enhance their students' creativity, as this encourages students to integrate general and subject-specific skills (Papaleontiou-Louca et al., 2014). Creativity is an essential condition for development and improvement, and fostering creativity through education is a categorical imperative for contemporary society. The school-age period is considered optimal for influencing students through strategies aimed at enhancing creativity (Kusin and Sollárová, 2002). According to current educational policy documents in Slovakia, developing students' creativity is one of the main goals of the education system. However, future teachers often lack professional training in creativity and key competency development, and existing training opportunities are insufficient. As a result, teacher education graduates enter schools lacking these competencies and in practice, subsequently either act intuitively or revert to traditional teaching patterns.

If we want to foster creativity in teachers, we must change the philosophy of teaching and redefine their professional roles and competencies. Thus, a paradoxical situation arises in the field of creativity development within education: we assume that creative teachers will foster creativity in their students, and therefore, future teachers are expected to become creative during their studies. Isolated creativity development programs are introduced, and specific courses are recommended, but these efforts are often sporadic and ineffective. In schools, students still predominantly learn by rote, sit passively at desks, listen to the teacher, solve identical problems using identical methods, and learn information they may never, or hardly ever, use. Primary school becomes merely preparation for secondary school, and some secondary schools function solely as preparation for university. Thus, school fails to prepare students for life, although it should. To change something, at first it is necessary to assess the current situation. The research we conducted at the DCAaE FE CPU in Nitra focused on this.

The aim of the research was to systematically map and analyze the perception of creativity and its role in the educational process among a specific group of respondents – future art teachers. The primary goal of the research was to identify and analyze the prevailing opinions and attitudes of future art teachers towards the definitions of creativity and its place and development in the educational process. The secondary goal was to obtain qualitative insights and reflections from the respondents on the given topic. The research has a descriptive character.

Materials and methods

For the purposes of our research, the questionnaire method was chosen as the primary data collection method. The use of an anonymous questionnaire allowed for the efficient collection of quantifiable data on attitudes and opinions regarding the defined aspects of creativity and its pedagogical implications. We used a partial adaptation of a questionnaire originally created for the European Commission and published in the publication "Creativity in Schools: A Survey of Teachers in Europe" (Cachia and Ferrari, 2010). The adapted questionnaire was designed to ascertain students' attitudes towards creativity. It was structured into two sections, the first dealing with the general concept of creativity and the second focusing on creativity in the educational environment.

Section 1. Respondents were presented with a series of statements defining creativity, specifically:

- Creativity is the ability to create something original.
- Creativity is about finding connections between things (previously unconnected).
- Creativity is the ability to produce something valuable.

Section 2. Respondents were presented with a series of statements about creativity in education, specifically:

- Creativity can be developed.
- Creativity can be assessed.
- Creativity is a fundamental skill that should be developed in school.

In both sections, an identical five-point Likert scale was used to express the degree of agreement. The degree of agreement with these definitions was assessed using the scale (1 – strongly agree, 2 – agree, 3 – no strong opinion / neutral, 4 – disagree, 5 – strongly disagree). The research involved 61 students from the Department of Art Creation and Education at Constantine the Philosopher University in Nitra. The respondents were studying within the field of Teacher Training and Educational Sciences, specifically in the study programs Teaching of Fine Arts (in combination) and Art Education. Data collection took place online during the summer semester of the academic year 2024/2025.

Results

Table 1: Level of agreement with definitions of creativity (N=61).

Definition	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total Resp.
1. Creativity is the ability to produce something original.	13 (21,3%)	37 (60,7%)	5 (8,2%)	6 (9,8%)	0 (0%)	61
2. Creativity is about finding connections between things that were previously unrelated.	13 (21,3%)	38 (62,3%)	8 (13,1%)	2 (3,3%)	0 (0%)	61
3. Creativity is the ability to produce something valuable.	14 (23%)	25 (41,0%)	10 (16,4%)	12 (19,7%)	0 (0%)	61

Table 1 shows the following results:

Creativity as originality: As many as 82% of respondents (the sum of "strongly agree" and "agree") perceive creativity as the ability to create something original. This indicates a very strong identification with this definition. Only 9.8% of respondents disagreed, and 8.2% had no strong opinion. Originality is therefore perceived as a key and little-questioned aspect of creativity. Creativity as finding connections: This

definition achieved the highest overall agreement, with 83.6% of respondents agreeing or strongly agreeing that creativity is about connecting previously unconnected things. Only 3.3% of respondents disagreed with this definition, which is the least among all three. Slightly more respondents (13.1%) were neutral compared to the definition of originality. Nevertheless, this definition (associative thinking, connecting) is also perceived as a very significant part of creativity. Creativity as the production of value: 63.9% of respondents agree or strongly agree with this definition. Although this is a lower, but still majority, level of agreement compared to the previous two definitions, the level of disagreement and neutrality is significantly higher. As many as 19.7% of respondents disagree with this definition, and 16.4% are neutral. This is considerably more than for the definitions of originality and connecting.

Table 2: Level of agreement with statement of creativity in education (N=61).

Statement	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Total Resp.
1. Creativity can be developed.	40 (65.6%)	19 (31.1%)	2 (3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	61
2. Creativity can be assessed.	2 (3.3%)	30 (49.2%)	21 (34.4%)	7 (11.5%)	1 (1.6%)	61
3. Creativity is a fundamental skill that should be developed in school.	21 (34.4%)	32 (52.5%)	7 (11.5%)	1 (1.6%)	0 (0.0%)	61

Table 2 shows the following results:

Development of Creativity ("Creativity can be developed"): Extremely high agreement, with 96.7% of respondents (the sum of "strongly agree" and "agree") believing that creativity can be developed. No one expressed disagreement. Assessment of Creativity ("Creativity can be assessed"): Ambiguous attitudes, this statement elicited the most dispersed responses. Only a narrow majority (52.5%) agrees with the assessment of creativity. A very significant portion of respondents (34.4%) has no strong opinion on this issue, indicating significant uncertainty or indecisiveness. Approximately 13.1% (the sum of "disagree" and "strongly disagree") believe that creativity cannot be assessed. Creativity as a Fundamental Skill ("Creativity is a fundamental skill that should be developed in school"): Very high agreement, with a total of 86.9% of respondents (the sum of "strongly agree" and "agree") considering creativity a fundamental skill for school education. Low levels of disagreement and neutrality: Disagreement was minimal (1.6%), and only 11.5% of respondents took a neutral stance.

Discussion

The results of the first part of the research show that respondents (future art teachers) most strongly associate creativity with the ability to find new connections (83.6%

agreement) and closely followed by producing something original (82.0% agreement). There is very high agreement and minimal disagreement with both of these definitions. Conversely, the definition linking creativity to the production of something valuable is accepted less unequivocally. Although a majority agrees with it (63.9%), almost a fifth of respondents expressed disagreement, and another significant portion (16.4%) remained neutral. It seems, therefore, that for this group of future teachers, novelty (originality) and process (finding connections) are key, while the requirement of external "value" of the result is perceived as less essential or more problematic. The results of the second part of the research show an interesting picture of the attitudes of future art teachers: there is a strong and unambiguous belief that creativity can be developed (almost 97% agreement) and that it is a fundamental skill that belongs in schools (almost 87% agreement). Conversely, there is significant uncertainty and disagreement in opinions on whether creativity can be assessed (only 52.5% agreement, but as many as 34.4% neutral). It seems that respondents are convinced of the importance and developability of creativity in the school context, but they struggle with the question of its evaluation and measurement. This finding may have important implications for the preparation of future teachers – they need not only methods for developing creativity but also discussion and tools (or at least an awareness of the limits) for its assessment.

Conclusion

The presented research focused on mapping the perception of creativity and its place in education among a sample of 61 art teacher training students at Constantine the Philosopher University in Nitra. Future art teachers are strongly convinced of the importance of developing creativity in schools, understanding it mainly through the prism of originality and the ability to connect ideas. They believe that this development is possible, but at the same time, they face significant uncertainty or skepticism regarding the possibilities of formally assessing creativity. This discrepancy between the emphasis on development and the uncertainty in assessment may stem precisely from the understanding of creativity as a complex process focused on novelty, which is difficult to quantify or measure objectively using traditional school methods, especially if it is less tied to the concept of external "value." It would be interesting to compare the results of our research with results in other countries, as the formative influence of cultural context is important in the perception of creativity, and students' ideas about creativity differ across countries, even within the same artistic discipline (Štěpánková, 2023).

These findings have important implications for practice and further teacher training. So far, there have been two main challenges: the first was to clarify for students what creativity really is, especially how the perception of the general public differs from that of experts regarding creativity and its aspects. Our second task was to teach students specific methods for developing creativity in art education. Both of these goals are being met intuitively in practical disciplines, partially in theoretical ones, and specifically in didactic disciplines. Students are consciously learning to develop fluency, flexibility, originality, imagination, fantasy, and elaboration in art activities (Figure 1), which are applicable in their future practice (Satková, 2022). Visual tasks focused on aspects of creativity are becoming part of seminar papers. Students – future teachers – thus gain a tool for understanding aspects of creativity through experience. The third challenge arising from the research is to teach students to evaluate creativity (also) in art education, and not to rely solely on psychologically focused disciplines.

Figure 1

Tasks for developing creativity (drawing and painting). Left: tasks of the type "invent, improve, design, imagine." Center: synesthetic stimuli (taste, smell, sound, touch of specific food or objects). Right: representation of emotions (how I feel, how I want to feel, how a living being feels, how an inanimate object feels), and representation of physical sensations (how I breathe, how my heart beats, how my hair grows).

Creativity is an important part of a teacher's personality. In order for an art teacher to perceive, develop, and evaluate students' creativity, they must learn this through their own experience at university. In our opinion, personal experience is the most important part of teaching at university, and the ability to transfer acquired skills to students, as well as the ability to initiate their new experiences, are among the key strategies that future teachers should acquire.

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